

PIACERE

Deliverable D2.4

PIACERE DevSecOps Framework – v2

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Abstract:	This deliverable (D2.4) is v2 of the same-named deliverable D2.3. This deliverable showcases the integration of all the components developed by the other technical WPs in the PIACERE DevSecOps Framework. Different versions of the PIACERE DevSecOps Framework are provided following an incremental approach. The first version was an initial prototype with the core functionalities implemented; the second version augments these functionalities taking into consideration the feedback coming for the use cases; the final version will include corrections and feedback coming from the implementation of the use cases.
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Terms and abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
BPMN	Business Process Model and Notation
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
CSEP	Canary Sandbox Environment Provisioner, component of PIACERE WP5
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
DevOps	Development and Operations
DevSecOps	Development, Security and Operations
DMC	DOML Model Checker
DMN	Decision Model and Notation
DoA	Description of Action
DOML	DevSecOps Modelling Language, as provided by PIACERE WP3
DMC	DOML Model Checker
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
ICG	Infrastructural Code Generator, component of PIACERE WP3
IDE	Integrated Development Environment, component of PIACERE WP3
IEC	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue, component of PIACERE WP5
IEM	IaC Execution Manager, component of PIACERE WP5
IOP	IaC Optimization Platform, component of PIACERE WP5
ISR	IaC Scan Runner
KR	Key Result
KR13	Key Result 13 – PIACERE DevSecOps framework – the integration key result that is presented in this deliverable
MC	Monitoring Controller
PMC	Performance Monitoring Controller
PRC	PIACERE Runtime Controller
SH	Self-Healing
SW	Software
TSR	Technical Specification Report (e.g., this document)

Executive Summary

This document is the second version of same-named D2.3. It comes with the same structure but updated contents and dedicated subsections discussing important differences since v1 so that it is easy to see the changes, yet the document remains self-contained. Additionally, in v2 we report on the CI/CD approach applied in the PIACERE project to deliver the individual components as well as the entire integrated framework.

This document describes the integration of the PIACERE framework v2 as a whole (Key Result 13 [KR13] v2) and acts as the Technical Specification Report (TSR) for the integrated PIACERE framework and the reported new software – PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC), also in v2. The PRC orchestrates the runtime of the PIACERE framework. The integration options of the IDE are also discussed as the IDE is the central point of PIACERE framework's design time.

The work reported here has been done as part of Task 2.3 (T2.3) in Work Package 2 (WP2) but it involves all other technical WPs, that is WP3, WP4, WP5, and WP6, as they provide the tools that compose the PIACERE framework. The PRC interacts with tools of the PIACERE runtime, i.e., those from WP5 and WP6.

The document starts with an introduction to the contents. Next, it has an explanation of the scope of integration – this lays ground for the rest of the document. It is important to note that this document does not dive into the WP-internal details of integration, e.g., those found mostly in WP6 work but also in parts of other packages. Then, it moves onto the description of integration points considered in this integration work which describe how the integration was conducted. After that, sections on PRC implementation and usage are included which put the PRC in context and describe it in detail. Finally, a conclusions section and appendix on Camunda (which is an important part of the current implementation of the PRC) close the document.

The main result of this deliverable is the integrated PIACERE framework and the PRC. Together they allow the PIACERE user to reap the benefits of all the PIACERE tooling provided in the first two years (i.e., by month 24) of the project and showcase that the PIACERE-provided tools can be used together.

Next, final version of this deliverable (v3, due month 33) will be based on this v2, updating it to adjust to changes made in the integrated components and possibly polishing the integration details as needed.

1 Introduction

1.1 About this deliverable

This document contains the details of the integration of the PIACERE framework v2 as a whole (KR13 v2) and is the TSR for it and the PRC v2. It also describes the CI/CD effort in the PIACERE project. This is v2 of same-named D2.3.

The integration involves all tools produced as part of other technical WPs, i.e., from WP3 to WP6. The PRC orchestrates the runtime and interacts with runtime tools from WP5 and WP6. The goal of this deliverable is to put the technical results in context and present their details as well as their usage. This v2 summarises also the changes made between v1 and v2 of the tools' interfaces and their integration.

This document does not concern itself with internal integration of components inside their respective deliverables as is the case with WP6 tooling as well as parts of other WPs.

1.2 Document structure

The document is comprised of 9 sections split into subsections. In v2 of the document, major content sections include subsections on updates since v1. The 1st section is this introduction. The 2nd section describes the scope of integration. The 3rd section goes into detail on the integration points. The 4th section introduces PRC's architecture and technical aspects. The 5th section describes the usage side of PRC. The 6th section offers conclusion. The 7th section contains references. Finally, the 8th section is an appendix on Camunda [1].

2 Scope of integration

This section lays the ground for understanding the integration of the PIACERE DevSecOps framework, also called PIACERE framework or simply PIACERE. The scope is described here along with main points of integration.

2.1 Changes since v1

There are no major changes in the scope of integration and thus this section remains mostly unchanged in principles. However, there is one major addition on CI/CD in the PIACERE project. All mentions and references of v1 have been updated to v2. We also don't report any deviations from the planned workflow as described in [D2.2](#) as the deviations reported in D2.3 have been incorporated in D2.2 and no new ones have been identified. The chosen integration modes with IDE have been clarified near the end of its subsection, and the plans for the upcoming, tighter integration with IDE have been laid out. The delivery has been optimised slightly not to depend on Ansible for installation (docker-compose is the sole requirement).

2.2 Components used in the integration of v2

In the first version of the PIACERE framework, the components used for integration are all those available at month 24 of the project. They are summarised, along with the respective Key Results and Deliverables in the table below (Table 1 PIACERE Framework v2 components). Various sections refer back to these deliverables if the reader wants to know more about the behaviour of a particular tool.

Table 1 PIACERE Framework v2 components

Key Results ¹	Deliverable	Component name
KR13	D2.4 (this one)	PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC)
KR3	D3.5	Infrastructural Code Generator (ICG)
KR2	D3.8	Integrated Development Environment (IDE)
KR5	D4.2	DOML Model Checker (DMC)
KR6, KR7	D4.5	IaC Scan Runner (ISR)
KR10	D5.2	IaC Execution Manager (IEM)
KR8	D5.5	Canary Sandbox Environment Provisioner (CSEP)
KR9	D5.8	IaC Optimization Platform (IOP)
KR9	D5.8	Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC)
KR11, KR12	D6.2	Monitoring Controller (MC)
KR11	D6.2	Performance Monitoring Controller (PMC)
KR11	D6.2	Performance Self-Learning
KR11	D6.2	Self-Healing (SH)
KR11, KR12	D6.2	Security Monitoring and Self-Learning

All components used for the integration described in this deliverable (except the IDE) have their interfaces follow the popular REST API practice and are described in the OpenAPI [2] format. Certain details on interfaces and the interaction with them are described in section 3. The IDE is a desktop component and thus does not offer a REST API.

¹ After a longer inspection, one may notice KR1 and KR4 missing from the table. However, they are DOML (DevSecOps Modelling Language) and its extensions, respectively, and thus are not providing software components for integration.

Additionally, an external, helper component is used in v2 integration – GitLab – serving as the DOML & IaC Repository. In practice, any Git repository hosting solution is a viable replacement.

2.3 Main points of integration

This section describes two main points of integration in the PIACERE workflow – the IDE and the PRC (PIACERE Runtime Controller). The latter’s details are reported in this deliverable.

2.3.1 IDE: Design time to runtime

One of the pivotal tools of the PIACERE project is the IDE – being a Graphical User Interface (GUI) of the PIACERE framework, it supports the design time of the PIACERE Framework and is a gateway to the runtime. Several other Key Results (KRs) of the project are integrated with the IDE using one of integration mechanisms that IDE and these technologies commonly provide. The PIACERE IDE is customized with suitable plug-ins that integrate with the different tools, to minimize the learning curve and simplify the adoption of the PIACERE DevSecOps IaC approach.

Figure 1: PIACERE IDE integration options

Several integration patterns, focusing on the Eclipse plugin architecture, are available. The proposed ones are:

1. **Native Extension/plugin.** With this option, the tool will be integrated as an Eclipse plugin and will be embedded into the PIACERE IDE:

Figure 2: Eclipse Plugin - Integration mechanism

2. **External Service: Backend Service.** This option allows to integrate an external Tool Service which could receive (for example, through a REST API) a DOML model ([D3.1](#)) and any necessary configuration to perform some task, e.g., storing its results in a repository.

Figure 3: External Service: Backend Service

3. **External Service: Interactive Service.** In this case, the external Tool Service provides a response to the PIACERE IDE (either directly or via a callback) with some tool-generated resources that can then be retrieve and stored by the IDE.

Figure 4: Interactive Service

4. **External Service: Interactive Service with visual (Editor/Viewer) feedback.** This final case is an extension of the previous one where it is required to provide some kind of Eclipse extension to visualize or to manage/edit tool-generated resources.

Figure 5: Interactive Service with visual feedback

The PIACERE tools integrated with the IDE can be grouped into two types. Design-time tools, which allow designing/defining the solution to be deployed, and runtime tools, which try to implement the designed system. All PIACERE tools have been integrated using a REST approach (as described in the next section “Integrations implementation”) which corresponds to patterns 2 and 3 above. Each tool publishes an API well defined using the OpenAPI notation. These APIs are invoked via the different menus and submenus of the IDE and the endpoints are configurable. Some tools will require a visual interface to interact with or to show the results in a human-friendly manner (i.e., follow pattern 4 above). These interfaces will be developed and included in the future version of the IDE.

Figure 6: IDE preferences menu for PIACERE

2.3.2 PRC: Control of the runtime

The other pivotal tool of the PIACERE project is the PRC – PIACERE Runtime Controller – which orchestrates the runtime part of the PIACERE framework and is a bridge for the IDE to go from design time to runtime. Various runtime components are interacted with and interact with the PRC. The details of PRC are reported in this deliverable in sections 4 and 5. This section is kept here short only to maintain the structure.

2.4 Delivery of the integrated components

All components were developed concurrently and their code history was tracked using the Git version control system. The **y2** branch tracks the progress for year 2 of the PIACERE project. All components, except the IDE, are containerised and were co-installed on the project-internal integration server. The Dockerfile [3] and docker-compose [4] recipes are available for easy recreation of the integration environment. Each component has a dedicated internal network which co-hosts the various subcomponents the tool might have. All REST API endpoints are exposed on a common network to allow for communication between the components. Access multiplexing is done with Traefik [5]. The PIACERE framework installation is done entirely using docker-compose.

2.5 Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery (CI/CD)

In addition to the “point releases” and their deployments maintained for demos and manual testing and experimentation, the PIACERE project has adopted a CI/CD strategy that validates each change to any of the PIACERE subcomponents. This is done with the help of GitLab CI/CD. Each Merge Request (MR) runs a set of tests (code linting, container image building, unit tests, integration tests) and their results determine whether the MR can be merged. The integration test deploys the entire centralised PIACERE framework (i.e., all components except the IDE which runs on user’s desktop) and runs simple flows against the deployed solution using example DOML documents and the OpenStack cloud deployed by PIACERE Canary Sandbox Environment Provisioner (CSEP). This ensures that the components work in tandem: that they

can be installed together, run together and, most importantly, used together in a coherent manner as defined by the PIACERE project.

3 Integrations implementation

This section describes the implementations of integration points – between main integration points and the other tools that are invoked or invoke the main integration points. The order of components in section names is: *invoker – invoked*. The invoked component is described in the context of being invoked by the invoker.

3.1 Changes since v1

Most integrations have been improved between v1 and v2. Most notably, additional tools, like IOP, now support accepting and outputting DOML directly. The IDE integrations have been enhanced. The monitoring-related integrations are now also more mature and thus their descriptions are also more detailed. Regarding minor but observable content changes, there are some removals of content which was deemed unnecessary (e.g., sample SQL scripts).

3.2 IDE&IOP – IEC

The Infrastructural Elements Catalogue (IEC) stores information about the services available at service providers, and classify them based on their properties. as well as the instances of each of these services deployed by the PIACERE infrastructure. The Catalogue is also expected to receive and offer information about the status of the deployed instances.

Behaviour

The IEC is part of the optimization component and is not intended to be used directly by the user. Instead, it is used behind the scenes (by the IOP and the IDE mainly). This use is made via the APIs provided by the IEC and is transparent to the final user.

Figure 7: IDE - IEC tab

However, the Catalogue provides a GUI (Graphical User Interface) that allows user interaction to check and edit the contained information. The GUI enables the create, read, update and delete (CRUD) capabilities for several entities: services, service classes and instances (Figure 8).

Placere IEC v0.0.1-SNAPSHOT Home * Services * Service Classes * Instances Administration Language Account

Welcome to Piacere IEC!

Infrastructural Elements Catalogue

You are logged in as user "admin".

	AIMES	Amazon	Arsys	Azure	Google	CloudSigma
Database	0 service(s)	4 service(s)	0 service(s)	2 service(s)	2 service(s)	0 service(s)
Storage	0 service(s)	2 service(s)	4 service(s)	3 service(s)	2 service(s)	0 service(s)
Virtual Machine	0 service(s)	11 service(s)	9 service(s)	6 service(s)	2 service(s)	1 service(s)

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Figure 8. IEC web Graphical User Interface

The IEC receives information from different sources. What we have called “static information”, concerns the available services provided by the CSPs. This information is pre-loaded in the IEC database using an SQL script.

The IEC also provides a REST API that can be accessed for automation purposes.

Input

The interaction between the IDE and the IEC is performed through the API. The REST API enables the interaction through a single endpoint (*/catalogue*). Currently, we include only one method that is called by the IDE – GET */api/root-serv*– GET */api/root-service/catalogue* (see Figure 9) – to obtain all the services present in the IEC.

root-service-resource Root Service Resource

GET /api/root-services/catalogue getAllRootServicesCatalogue

Parameters

Name	Description
serviceClassId.equals integer(\$int64) (query)	<input type="text" value="serviceClassId.equals"/>
serviceClassId.greaterThan integer(\$int64) (query)	<input type="text" value="serviceClassId.greaterThan"/>
serviceClassId.greaterThanOrEqualTo integer(\$int64) (query)	<input type="text" value="serviceClassId.greaterThanOrEqualTo"/>
serviceClassId.in array[integer] (query)	<input type="button" value="Add integer item"/>
serviceClassId.lessThan integer(\$int64) (query)	<input type="text"/>

Figure 9: IEC REST API.

Output

The output that receives the IDE will be the list of services in a json format. In the next figure, there can be seen a small excerpt of the response, showing part of the “C1_Spain” service of type “Virtual Machine”.

```
[
  {
    "id": 1,
    "serviceName": "C1_Spain",
    "deletedDate": null,
    "serviceClass": {
      "id": 3,
      "serviceName": "Virtual Machine",
      "deletedDate": null
    },
    "serviceAttributeValues": [
      {
        "id": 1,
        "serviceAttributeValue": "00EU",
        "unitValue": "",
        "serviceAttributeType": {
          "id": 1,
          "name": "Region",
          "nfrName": "Region",
          "isEnumeration": true,
          "isForm": false,

```

```

        "isCommon": true,
        "isFunctionRequirement": false,
        "units": "",
        "unitFactor": "",
        "unitRule": "LIKE",
        "evalRule": ""
    }
},
{
    "id": 2,
    "serviceAttributeValue": "SPEU",
    "unitValue": "",
    "serviceAttributeType": {
        "id": 2,
        "name": "Zone",
        "nfrName": "Zone",
        "isEnumeration": true,
        "isForm": false,
        "isCommon": true,
        "isFunctionRequirement": false,
        "units": "",
        "unitFactor": "",
        "unitRule": "LIKE",
        "evalRule": ""
    }
},
(...)

```

Figure 10: Excerpt of the output response to the IDE call.

The integrated PIACERE IDE gathers this information and offers a way of using the content of the catalogue through a specific view (the “IEC View”), where the services are listed, grouped by the element type (a further click on any of the services shows its properties).

3.3 IDE – DOML Model Checker

The DOML Model Checker (DMC) is a tool that statically analyses IaC for compliance with a pre-defined or user-supplied specification. It reports to the user whether the specification is satisfied or not.

Behaviour

The user requests the verification of the currently displayed DOML model in the IDE through an appropriate user interaction (e.g., a button or menu entry). Then, the IDE sends to the DMC a model checking request containing the DOML model. The DMC then processes the IaC and sends the outcome of model checking back to the IDE. Finally, the IDE displays the verification outcome to the user by means of a text message in a pop-up window.

Figure 11: IDE – DOML model checker menu option

The interaction between the IDE and the DMC is performed through REST APIs. The REST API enables the interaction by providing one single endpoint (*/modelcheck*), which accepts a POST request containing the elements listed in the Input section. The result (described in the Output section) of the model checking process is then sent to the client as the answer to its POST request (Figure 12 DMC REST API).

Figure 12 DMC REST API

Input

The DMC receives from the IDE a verification request containing:

- The DOML model to be verified in a machine-readable format, possibly XMI (required),
- A string describing the requirement to be verified (optional, currently not supported).

Output

The DMC answers with:

- A string stating the verification outcome (**required**). This can be either “sat”, meaning the model satisfies the requirements, “unsat”, meaning the model does not satisfy the requirements, or “dontknow”, meaning the model checking process was inconclusive due to a timeout.
- A string describing the issue(s) found in the model (**optional**, set if there are issues).

Figure 13: IDE – Model checker output

3.4 IDE – IOP

The IaC Optimization Platform is a tool for optimizing the IaC based on the constraints in the DOML model.

Behaviour

In a nutshell, the IOP is responsible for finding the best possible infrastructure given the input data received. In other words, the optimizer uses an optimization algorithm to find an optimized deployment configuration of the IaC on the appropriate infrastructural elements that best meet the predefined constraints, i.e., are optimal. This information is supposed to be presented to the PIACERE user.

The IOP offers an embedded Swagger UI (Figure 14) to facilitate the understanding and usage by the IDE.

Figure 14 Swagger UI page for IOP

Input

In v2, the input data is accepted in the DOML format.

Output

Once the IOP completes the optimization, it returns as output an updated DOML model.

For details on IOP's behaviour, please see D5.8.

3.5 IDE – ICG

The Infrastructural Code Generator (ICG) is the PIACERE component that allows generating executable infrastructural code (IaC) from models written in DOML.

Behaviour

The ICG communicates with the IDE through REST API. The user can request the conversion of the DOML model in IaC code by the IDE menu selection "Generate IaC Code", as shown in Figure 15.

Figure 15: IDE - ICG "Generate IaC Code" menu option

If the conversion is selected, the ICG expects a POST (Figure 16) call from the IDE containing the model with all the necessary data. After the ICG has generated all the IaC files they will be sent back as a response (compressed in a tar.gz package) and will be available to the user through the IDE.

Figure 16 ICG REST API

The ICG also provides logs related to the process of generation of the IaC files, containing errors, warnings and info useful to the end user. These logs need to be exported to the user in a way that is easily readable and comprehensible.

Lastly, the ICG uses configuration files on the local filesystem that allow the extensibility of the tool through the definition of the components and templates, which are going to be expanded when new components are added. To update these files, the filesystem can be mounted from an external source where the IDE can access them.

Further details about the ICG component can be found in deliverable D3.5.

Inputs

The input of the ICG is the DOMLx model.

Outputs

The output of the ICG is a compressed package (tar.gz extension) containing the IaC files.

Figure 17: ICG IaC generated folder

3.6 IDE – IaC Scan Runner

The IaC Scan Runner is a component providing a single interface to the functionalities of IaC Security Inspector and Component Security Inspector. This component includes multiple IaC and component checks that are used to perform scanning of IaC and returning the discovered common security vulnerabilities and misconfigurations.

Behaviour

IaC Scan Runner is usually set up in a Docker container and gets exposed as a REST API service that comes with OpenAPI Specification that allows users to interact with the API through browser (Figure 18). There is a big difference from previous versions - API is now divided into two sections. First section includes test endpoints which are used to test all available checks – this approach was used in previous editions of IDE. Using the `test/checks` endpoint, the API enables the user to list and filter the supported checks (those are described thoroughly within IaC Scanner documentation: <https://xlab-si.github.io/iac-scanner-docs/>). Apart from IaC and component distinctions, checks can also be local (executing on the machine where IaC Scan Runner is running) or remote (executing partially or wholly on the remote service, e.g., Snyk, SonarCloud, etc.). Checks can be enabled (using `test/enable` endpoint) or disabled (using `test/disable` endpoint) for running. Some of them are disabled by default and need to be configured (via `test/configure` endpoint by supplying necessary configuration files or/and credentials) before running. When configuration steps are done, checks can be run by calling `test/scan`, which expects the compressed IaC file and a list of checks to be executed while scanning (if no list is supplied, then API runs all enabled checks).

Second section, named Project, serves as per project configured checks. That means that user can define specific configuration per project and this is a proposed way to allow co-existence of multiple scans and temporary storing all results for some time. Project is created by calling `POST /project`. Checks can be enabled, disabled, and configured in the same way as it is described in first section of the API. It is also possible, to set project configuration beforehand with appropriate JSON file (an example JSON can be seen in <https://xlab-si.github.io/iac-scanner-docs/>). Once appropriate configuration file is created you can create new configuration instance by calling `/project/configuration` and set its content by uploading your configuration file to `project/configuration/parameters`. Configuration then needs to be bind to a project, calling `/project/configuration/bind` endpoint. Once everything is configured you can initiate scan by

calling `/project/scan`. Each scan result is now saved and can be viewed by `/project/results` or deleted by `/project/results/{result_uuid}`.

laC Scan Runner REST API 0.1.9 OAS3

/openapi.json

Service that scans your Infrastructure as Code for common vulnerabilities

Test LEGECY, used for testing the tool ^

- GET `/test/checks` Retrieve and filter checks
- PUT `/test/{check_name}/enable` Enable check for running
- PUT `/test/{check_name}/disable` Disable check for running
- PUT `/test/{check_name}/configure` Configure check for running
- POST `/test/scan` Initiate laC scan

Project ^

- GET `/project` Retrieve list of projects for given user or all projects if no user provided
- POST `/project` Generate new scan project for given user as creator
- POST `/project/configuration/bind` Assign configuration to the given scan project
- POST `/project/configuration` Create a new scan project configuration
- POST `/project/configuration/parameters` Set the parameters for configuration by given id
- POST `/project/scan` Initiate laC scan
- GET `/project/results` Retrieve particular scan result by given uuid
- DELETE `/project/results/{uuid}` Delete particular scan result by given uuid
- GET `/project/checks` Retrieve and filter checks
- PUT `/project/{check_name}/enable` Enable check for running
- PUT `/project/{check_name}/disable` Disable check for running
- PUT `/project/{check_name}/configure` Configure check for running

Figure 18: Section from Swagger UI page for laC Scan Runner REST API

```
curl -X 'GET' \
  'http://127.0.0.1:8080/test/checks' \
  -H 'accept: application/json'
```

Request URL
http://127.0.0.1:8080/test/checks

Server response

Code	Details
200	<pre>{ "name": "opera-tosca-parser", "description": "Opera TOSCA parser can validate TOSCA YAML templates and CSARs", "enabled": true, "configured": true, "target_entity_type": "IaC" }, { "name": "ansible-lint", "description": "Ansible Lint is a command-line tool for linting playbooks, roles and collections aimed towards any Ansible users", "enabled": true, "configured": true, "target_entity_type": "IaC" }, { "name": "steampunk-scanner", "description": "A quality scanner for Ansible tasks, playbooks, roles and collections", "enabled": false, "configured": false, "target_entity_type": "IaC and component" }, { "name": "tflint", "description": "A Pluggable Terraform Linter", "enabled": true, "configured": true, "target_entity_type": "IaC" }</pre>

Figure 19 Filtering out check for Terraform in the laC Scan Runner REST API

The laC scan will be performed from the IDE just after the ICG generates laC code from the DOML. The idea is that a user would be able to locate the laC code within the IDE and, from the

context menu, send it directly to the IaC Scan Runner Service. The output of the IaC scan runner will be a text that would be retrieved back to the IDE and presented to the user.

Figure 20. IaC Scan Runner menu option

Inputs

Input to the IaC Scan Runner is a compressed package (zip or tar/compressed-tar), including the IaC code.

Outputs

Output is a text file (JSON or HTML) that includes the content – warnings and messages – that describe the issues in IaC and the return codes from each of the selected checks.

3.7 IDE – CSEP

The Canary Sandbox Environment Provisioner (CSEP) is a tool providing the PIACERE user with the ability to create (provision) Canary Sandbox Environments based on OpenStack.

Behaviour

It is expected that the PIACERE user will be able to issue new deployment requests and browse existing deployments from the IDE.

Figure 21. CSEP menu

The CSEP provides a REST API with endpoints required to facilitate this (Figure 22). The CSEP renders its own API documentation at the `/docs` path which allows the integrator to inspect the API requirements.

GET	/deployments/	Get All Deployments	▼
POST	/deployments/	Post Deployment	▼
GET	/deployments/{deployment_name}	Get Deployment	▼
DELETE	/deployments/{deployment_name}	Delete Deployment	▼

Figure 22 CSEP API endpoints

There is a *dummy* deployment type provided for integrator's convenience which does not require actual target hosts to be available and the integration can be tested at no cost.

Inputs

As the input, the deployment creation API accepts JSON documents describing the details of the requested deployment. Each deployment is identified by its name which is a user-provided string and has to be unique on that instance of CSEP. The creation of deployments is facilitated by the `POST /deployments/` method. The other methods do not require any input.

Outputs

As the output, the API offers JSON documents describing the details of managed deployments.

3.8 IDE – PRC

The PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC) is the orchestration tool of the PIACERE runtime. It is described in detail in this document in later sections.

Expected behaviour

The IDE uses PRC to control the runtime of PIACERE. The PRC allows to create new deployments and inspect the state of existing ones. The deployments are identified by their identifiers which

are mostly free-form names. Please refer to PRC REST API section in this document for details on the behaviour and inputs and outputs.

Figure 23. IDE – PRC menu and options

3.9 IDE – Monitoring Dashboard

The monitoring components allow gathering metric from the infrastructure resources that have been deployed by PIACERE framework. PIACERE supports two types of monitoring:

- The **Performance Monitoring** component focuses on gathering performance-related measures from the infrastructure resources. The measures are gathered by agents running in the infrastructure resources. Examples of metrics are memory use, disk use, processes, CPU usage, etc.
- The **Security Monitoring** component focuses on gathering security-related measures from the infrastructure resources. The measures are gathered by agents running in the infrastructure resources.

Behaviour

When a new IaC is deployed, an extra task is undertaken: the deployment of monitoring agents along with the infrastructure, and the configuration of the monitoring components. Then, the continuous gathering of performance/security metrics can start. These metrics are evaluated against the expected thresholds or SLAs and, if needed, alerts are sent to the Self-Healing component.

The IDE enables the user to reach the dashboards of the monitoring system. In the next image we show the current approach to provide access on the monitoring aspects from the IDE. In the next versions we will also include access to the self-healing component to provide access to the monitoring event logs and self-healing strategies.

Figure 24 – Monitoring access from deployment context menu

This is done via the Performance Monitoring Controller (PMC) which offers a REST API (Figure 25), the Security monitoring controller (Figure 26), and in the future the self-healing API (Figure 27).

Figure 25 Swagger UI page for PMC²

² <https://c.pm.ci.piacere.digital.tecnalia.dev/pmc/api/v1/webjars/swagger-ui/index.html?url=/pmc/api/v1/openapi.yaml>

Security Monitoring 1.1.1 OAS3

This is a PIACERE Security Monitoring API definition.

[Terms of service](#)

[Contact the developer](#)

Apache 2.0

[Find out more about Swagger](#)

Servers

/security-monitoring/v1

Authorize

self_learning ^

GET /ad_models v

DELETE /ad_models/{adModelId} v

GET /ad_models/{adModelId} v

POST /anomaly_detection_inference v

GET /config v

POST /config/reset v

Figure 26 OpenApi for SMC³

Self Healing Messages

Refresh List
+ Create a new Self Healing Message

ID	Origin	Application Id	Timestamp	Status	Error	Event Type	
2	psl	123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426614174000	23 Mar 2022 18:11:03	PROCESSED		EVENT_USAGE_IDLE_01	View Edit Delete
3	psl	123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426614174000	23 Mar 2022 18:12:03	PROCESSED		EVENT_USAGE_IDLE_01	View Edit Delete
4	psl	123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426614174000	23 Mar 2022 18:13:04	PROCESSED		EVENT_USAGE_IDLE_01	View Edit Delete
5	psl	123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426614174000	23 Mar 2022 18:14:04	PROCESSED		EVENT_USAGE_IDLE_01	View Edit Delete
6	psl	123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426614174000	23 Mar 2022 18:14:55	PROCESSED		EVENT_USAGE_IDLE_01	View Edit Delete
7	osl	123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-	23 Mar 2022	PROCESSED		EVENT_USAGE_IDLE_01	View Edit Delete

Figure 27 Event Logs in the SH⁴

Inputs

³ <https://sm.ci.piacere.digital.tecnalia.dev/security-monitoring/v1/openapi.json>

⁴ <https://sh.ci.piacere.digital.tecnalia.dev/admin/docs>

In order to retrieve the URL of dashboard for a specific deployment, the performance monitoring controllers provide a method to get the URL of the dashboard. As an example of this approach, we show the method can be explored and tested from the Swagger UI embedded in the performance monitoring controller, and the response schema can be seen in Figure 28.

```

TrackedDeployment {
  description:      Deployment identifier

  id*              string
                  id of the deployment

  dashboard_url*  string
                  url of the grafana dashboard
}

example: OrderedMap { "id": "123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426614174000", "dashboard_url":
"https://grafana.pmc.piacere.esilab.org/deployment/123e4567-e89b-12d3-a456-426614174000" }

```

Figure 28 PMC – get deployment response

Outputs

The outputs to the IDE are the created Grafana dashboards' access link. The dashboard is still in design phase and the current draft is presented in Figure 29.

Figure 29 Grafana monitoring dashboard draft

The output of the Monitoring system is reflected in one or more visual dashboards, where the metrics, thresholds, etc. can be consulted in a graphical/numerical view. At the time of writing, the dashboards are not designed yet, but a graphic or table is expected for each of the metrics gathered like memory, disk, CPU usage or availability. These dashboards are created on the fly, once the information of the deployed infrastructure is available. For this, pre-defined templates or the Grafana API can be used. Grafana dashboards are HTML elements, and will be integrated in the PIACERE IDE, as iframes or a similar technology. Moreover, Security Monitoring Dashboard provides Kibana dashboard showing an overview of security-related events (Figure 30) throughout the time of the infrastructure's lifecycle (from the time of deployment of Security Monitoring agents on the infrastructure – which is implicitly already included with the definition of the rest of Monitoring infrastructure within DOML).

Figure 30: Security Monitoring Dashboard shows Wazuh's Kibana dashboard.

3.10 PRC – IEM

The IEM serves the purpose of deployment and redeployment of IaC. It supports different IaC technologies present in the market and provides a common interface to execute the deployments of the different elements present in the PIACERE project. In addition, the current prototype handles the redeployment and tearing down of existing deployments.

Behaviour

The main purpose of the IEM is to handle the lifecycle of the deployments that are managed within PIACERE framework. The integration between the PRC and the IEM is handled by a REST API. The PRC can perform the following actions this way on the IEM: i) query the status of all active deployments, ii) trigger a deployment, iii) query the status of a particular deployment, and iii) delete a deployment. These actions are depicted in Figure 31 as REST API endpoints.

Figure 31 IEM Endpoints

Inputs

The POST `/deployments/` triggers or updates a deployment in the infrastructure. The IEM needs a few fields to kick off a deployment, the schema for calling this endpoint is showcased in Figure 32.

```
{
  "deployment_id": "string",
  "repository": "string",
  "commit": "string",
  "credentials": {
    "aws": {
      "access_key_id": "string",
      "secret_access_key": "string"
    },
    "azure": {
      "arm_client_id": "string",
      "arm_client_secret": "string",
      "arm_subscription_id": "string",
      "arm_tenant_id": "string"
    },
    "openstack": {
      "user_name": "string",
      "password": "string",
      "auth_url": "string",
      "project_name": "string",
      "region_name": "string",
      "domain_name": "string",
      "project_domain_name": "string",
      "user_domain_name": "string"
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 32 IEM PUT /deployments/ request schema.

The POST /undeploy/ serves the purpose of tearing down a particular deployment. In Figure 33, the request body required for the invocation of this endpoint is shown.

```
{
  "deployment_id": "string",
  "credentials": {
    "aws": {
      "access_key_id": "string",
      "secret_access_key": "string"
    },
    "azure": {
      "arm_client_id": "string",
      "arm_client_secret": "string",
      "arm_subscription_id": "string",
      "arm_tenant_id": "string"
    },
    "openstack": {
      "user_name": "string",
      "password": "string",
      "auth_url": "string",
      "project_name": "string",
      "region_name": "string",
      "domain_name": "string",
      "project_domain_name": "string",
      "user_domain_name": "string"
    }
  }
}
```

Figure 33 IEM DELETE /deployments/ request schema

Outputs

The output is present for `GET /deployments/{deployment_id}` and its schema is shown in Figure 34.

Figure 34 IEM `GET /deployments/{deployment_id}` response schema.

3.11 PRC – Monitoring Controller

The monitoring controller (MC) is a utility component that aims to simplify the configuration of the monitoring, self-learning and self-healing component as PIACERE platform creates, updates and destroys deployments. It also isolates the PRC from changes in those mentioned components.

Behaviour

This component is in charge of the activation and deactivation of monitoring activities throughout all the monitoring components: performance monitoring, security monitoring, performance Self-learning and security Self-learning. It exposes a REST API (Figure 35).

It is expected that PRC calls this component when initiating new deployment to configure monitoring for it.

Figure 35 MC OpenAPI rendered in embedded Swagger UI

Inputs

The input is the deployment identifier of the deployment to be monitored.

Outputs

The only output is an acknowledge that the request has been received and it is being processed (that is, starting up monitoring and self-learning components).

3.12 Self-Healing – PRC

The PIACERE Runtime Controller (PRC) is the orchestration tool of the PIACERE runtime. It is described in detail in this document in later sections.

Expected behaviour

The Self-Healing uses PRC to issue self-healing requests on existing deployments should the need arise. The PRC allows this via a dedicated per-deployment endpoint. Each deployment is identified by an identifier which is a mostly free-form name. Self-Healing is able to choose the desired self-healing strategy. Please refer to PRC REST API section in this document for details on the behaviour and inputs and outputs.

The current set of strategies that affects the PRC are: redeploy, notify user, and halt. Moreover, in the future version, two new strategies are envisioned: the scaling and the ansible strategy. Both strategies are currently under development. These requests for triggering a specific strategy will be sent to the self-healing operation in the PRC.

Inputs

The information to be provided for the self-healing action is the strategy to be executed and a structure with the options for that operation. This will depend on the action to be performed.

Outputs

The output is the confirmation that the request has been received.

3.13 Monitoring Component – IEC

The purpose of this interaction is to add and update real time information about the quality (i.e., a set of attributes) pertaining to the infrastructure element.

Behaviour

The Monitoring gets real-time data from the different infrastructural elements used during the operation of the started deployments. This information will be sent back to the IEC to its future use in IOP to adjust the properties that are used during the filtering and selection of the infrastructure elements.

Monitoring will use the IEC REST API to keep some attributes up to date for each of the infrastructure elements in use. It will add and update information about the number of incidences with respect to performance, availability, and security.

Inputs

The information to be provided for IEC is a reference of the IEC element affected and the type of the value that is being updated and the actual value to be included.

Outputs

The output is the confirmation that the request has been processed and resources updated.

4 PRC Implementation

4.1 Changes since v1

The internals and behaviour of PRC have not changed between v1 and v2. There are only slight wording updates in this version. However, there is an extra subsection at the end of this section, discussing future updates to the PRC component.

4.2 Functional description

The PRC (PIACERE Runtime Controller) is the heart of the PIACERE runtime integration. It is the main component of the runtime called from the design-time tooling (IDE). It is also the main component coordinating the work of the runtime, i.e., calling the other specific tools delivered as part of the PIACERE framework for the runtime and allowing those tools to call back.

The runtime of PIACERE is responsible for ensuring that the designed infrastructure is deployed, monitored, self-healed, and optimized as expected. To this end, the basic concept in the runtime is deployment. Each deployment is managed individually and can be updated by providing an updated design (specifically, IaC). To align with the current trends, the IaC comes from the git version control system where it is versioned.

There were no PRC-specific requirements collected. The PRC satisfies the self-imposed requirement of being usable to realise the designed workflow.

The main innovation of PRC is the integration of runtime components to create a coherent workflow for deployment, its monitoring, self-healing and optimization.

4.2.1 Fitting into overall PIACERE Architecture

The PRC coordinates the workflow, the other tools themselves are concerned with work details. The PRC is responsible for calling the other tools at relevant times. To this end, it has to communicate with them using the interfaces they offer.

There are 3 tools that are called by the PRC v2:

- IEM (IaC Execution Manager): responsible for executing IaC, called due to creation of a new deployment, update of an existing deployment or in the course of a relevant self-healing strategy,
- IOP (IaC Optimisation Platform): responsible for proposing an optimised deployment design, called in the course of a relevant self-healing strategy,
- MC (Monitoring Controller): responsible for configuring the WP6 monitoring, self-learning and self-healing suite of tools.

There is 1 extra tool that is also used by the PRC and it is the central git repository (DOML&IaC Repository) of the deployment. In v2 this is meant to be used only for obtaining the repository contents, specifically the part relevant for IOP to do its job (propose an optimisation). PRC and other tools assume web (http-based) access to the repository.

PRC v2 itself is called by 2 PIACERE tools:

- IDE (the PIACERE GUI in Eclipse): the IDE is user's default starting point for interaction with PRC, the initial deployment request will likely originate from it,
- Self-Healing (SH): SH uses PRC to request the chosen self-healing strategy to be applied to the deployment.

4.3 Technical description

4.3.1 Prototype architecture

The architecture of PRC v2 is shown in Figure 36. The PRC is composed of 3 main components:

- PRC API,
- Camunda Platform,
- PRC Camunda Packages.

They are connected via dedicated interfaces.

Figure 36 PRC Architecture Diagram

4.3.2 Components description

The PRC API component offers the PRC REST API (HTTP) interface that can be used by the external world. This is to be used by other PIACERE tools, such as the IDE and Self-Healing. The interface itself is described in detail in the User Manual section. It connects with the Camunda Platform via Camunda Platform’s own REST API. The purpose of the PRC API is to abstract away the details of Camunda’s API and allow for the replacement of the internals in case such a need arises.

The Camunda Platform is the workhorse of the orchestration – it is a BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation) workflow and DMN (Decision Model and Notation) decision automation platform. A dedicated BPMN workflow has been designed for use in PRC. The Camunda Platform allows action extensibility via, e.g., Java Delegates and this mechanism has been chosen for the implementation of the 3rd component.

The PRC Camunda Packages offer a set of Java Delegates that extend the Camunda Platform to run PRC-specific actions. They are used, e.g., to invoke APIs of other PIACERE components.

4.3.3 Technical specifications

The proposed solution is based on the Camunda Platform – a platform for workflow and decision automation that supports BPMN and DMN standards. The choice of Camunda Platform has already been discussed in D2.1. The Camunda Platform version used is the latest at the time of writing – 7.16.0. The Camunda Platform runs in Java Runtime Environment (JRE). The version of JRE used is the latest version of Java 11.

The PRC Camunda Packages are also written in Java 11. They are compiled using the latest version of Java Development Kit (JDK) 11 and each functional class offers a JavaDelegate

interface. The project is managed by Maven (currently at version 3.6.0) and run as a Spring Boot application.

The PRC API is written in Python and tested with Python 3.10, but any modern Python (3.8+) should work as no bleeding-edge features of Python are used. The PRC API uses the FastAPI [6] framework, currently in version 0.73.0. This framework supports Asynchronous Server Gateway Interface (ASGI). ASGI must be understood by the used web server. The one chosen for this project is uvicorn [7], currently in version 0.17.5. FastAPI relies on Python's type annotations to handle API definition and validation of inputs and outputs. FastAPI also generates OpenAPI specification automatically and allows rendering docs in Swagger UI [8] and Redoc [9]. Finally, Pydantic [10] is used both indirectly, for the purposes of FastAPI, as well as directly for the management of settings (via environment variables). Pydantic's version is managed by FastAPI. Pydantic provides additional type annotations and validation of objects.

4.4 PRC workflow in BPMN

This section contains a description of the main PRC flow, modelled as BPMN and implemented with the Camunda Platform. Figure 38 presents the BPMN diagram of the process. The theory of BPMN is not described in this deliverable and we invite readers to approach this intuitively.

Figure 37 BPMN model of PRC

4.4.1 Main flow

In short, the idea of the process is to prepare a project and deploy it with IEM, check it in with Monitoring Controller, and then wait for a message to finish the process. In the meantime (usually while waiting for the last message), the process is kept alive, and two self-healing methods can be triggered. Below the flow is explained in detail.

1. Start process

2. Clone and prepare the process

This step is executed without interaction with the user. A repository is cloned to a specified directory, then a checkout to a specified commit is performed.

3. Deploy in IEM

This step is executed without interaction with the user. First, a deploy request is sent to IEM via REST API; then the process starts to actively wait for a deploy to complete by checking the IEM status every 30 seconds. Once finished, the result of the deployment is verified. If the deployment fails, the whole process is finished. Otherwise, the flow progresses to the next step.

4. Wait for the message to finish the deployment

At this step, the process is waiting for a specific message: *FinishTheDeploymentMessage*.

5. Finish event

4.4.2 Self-healing subprocesses

Apart from the main flow, the PRC process contains other subprocesses. They are non-interrupting, which means they do not cause the termination of the main process. They can be triggered at any time with an appropriate message, but a typical use case in the PRC is receiving them while the process is on hold, waiting for the finishing message. Below we present some examples of these subprocesses.

- **Self-healing with IEM**

Self-healing with IEM subprocess is triggered by an *IEMSelfHealingMessage*. As the name suggests, it communicates with IEM via its REST API to execute the self-healing. Generally, it works analogously to the early steps of the main flow, with minor implementation differences.

- **Self-healing with IOP**

Self-healing with IOP subprocess is triggered by sending an *IOPSelfHealingMessage*. It is executed by a simple request to IOP via its REST API.

Additional subprocesses will be included to cover other self-healing strategies such as: halt, notify user, ansible or scaling.

4.5 Future plans regarding PRC

As the PIACERE v2 integrated release focused on the ecosystem and the general integration (with CI/CD in the spotlight), the functionality of the PRC has not seen relevant changes. However, for the final release, there are plans of the tool owner partners to modify the APIs and enable new functionalities which will require amendments in the PRC.

One such change is the IEM switching to supporting accepting an IaC archive directly instead of a path to a Git repository. This way, only the PRC needs to be authorised to access the Git repository. Furthermore, the support for custom user IaC in the design phase means that PRC will need to integrate both PIACERE-generated and user's IaC and distribute it to tools that need it. Finally, the self-healing strategies start to come into shape and will need calling more PIACERE tools via the PRC.

All described above is progressing in design and development parallelly to this v2 integration work.

5 PRC Delivery and usage

5.1 Changes since v1

The PRC's delivery and usage has not changed since v1. Some wording has been improved. The licensing information has been updated to clarify that PRC is not a part of PIACERE open source.

5.2 Package information

PRCRestApi	The delivered package contains two main catalogs and a number of configuration files. The most important are listed below:
src/main	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ src directory contains the whole backend implementation, i.e., configuration classes which are responsible for running a server with the Camunda Platform, implementation of various workflow elements described in 4.4, and a BPMN diagram of the PRC process,
.env	
.gitignore	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ PRCRestApi directory is a Python project implementing the PRC API layer, containing all files required to build and start the service,
.gitlab-ci.yml	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ .env file contains environmental variables (e.g., addresses of the external tools),
Dockerfile	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ docker-compose.yml, Dockerfile, and pom.xml are configuration files for Docker and Maven systems.
LICENSE	
README.md	
docker-compose.yml	
pom.xml	

5.3 Installation instructions

The software is containerisable and the recipe is provided along with an example docker-compose deployment. The users are recommended to install a relatively modern Docker (19.03+) and docker-compose (1.29+). Then it is only a matter of running

```
docker-compose up -d
```

Figure 38 PRC package contents

to get the software running. Please note that the image might take a while to build before it can be used. The docker-compose command above will start both the Camunda Platform and the PRC API service.

5.4 User Manual

The PRC offers interfaces to allow for integration. These are dedicated to the tools expected to be able to integrate with PRC.

The main assumption is that the user is able to create a process instance which overlooks a particular deployment, allowing to trigger further actions on it. The deployment (process instance) should be identified by a name provided by the user (there could be an additional identifier, but the name has to be easily usable for integration purposes as it is passed in by the tools and passed on to the tools).

IDE actions:

- Creating a deployment
- Getting deployments
- Get details (status) of a deployment

- Update an existing deployment

Self-healing actions:

- Run a specific self-healing strategy on an existing deployment
 - The strategy defines the flow and its configuration in Camunda,
 - The process instance knows it's in a state that some strategy is running or that it is being updated from the IDE in which case the self-healing should be disabled (calls ignored) until the new deployment is in place and the monitoring has been notified.

5.4.1 PRC REST API

This section contains a detailed description of PRC REST API. The summary is presented in Figure 39.

GET	/deployments	Get All Deployments	▼
POST	/deployments	Create New Deployment	▼
POST	/deployments/{deployment_id}/self_heal	Trigger Self Healing	▼
POST	/deployments/{deployment_id}/finish	Finish The Deployment	▼
GET	/deployments/{deployment_id}	Get Deployment	▼

Figure 39 A summary of available PRC REST API endpoints

The API revolves around deployments, each identified by unique user-provide **deployment_id**. It can be a number, a name, or a mix of alphanumeric characters and symbols, except for '_' (underscore) and ',' (comma) and characters that could interact with URL syntax – this is a limitation of the Camunda Platform. For simplification, a recommended name is composed of letters and, optionally, numbers and whitespaces.

Below, a list of all exposed endpoints is presented.

- Create a new deployment:

POST /deployments

With a request body:

```
{
  "repository_url": "string",
  "deployment_id": "string",
  "commit_id": "string"
}
```

Where **repository_url** is an address of a git repository with a project to deploy, and **commit_id** is an optional commit identifier to be used instead of the default one.

Possible responses are confirmation with status code 200 or a validation error message with status code 422.

An example of a successful response with status code 200:

```
{
  "message": "Request received"
}
```

- Get a list of all deployments:

GET /deployments

The response is a list (potentially empty) of all deployments.

An example of a successful response with status code 200:

```
[
  {
    "deploymentName": "1"
  },
  {
    "deploymentName": "2"
  }
]
```

- Get a specific deployment:

GET /deployments/{deployment_id}

Possible responses are a deployment description with status code 200 or a resource not found as an error with status code 404.

An example of a successful response with status code 200:

```
{
  "deploymentName": "1"
}
```

- Initiate a self-healing process or optimization process:

POST /deployments/{deployment_id}/self_heal

With request body:

```
{
  "method": "method_name"
}
```

Where **method** is a *redeploy* for initiating the self-healing process with IEM tool or *optimize* for initiating the optimization with IOP tool.

Possible responses are a confirmation with status code 200 or an error message with status code 404 (meaning that `deployment_id` does not exist) or 422 (the **method** parameter is invalid or the request body is otherwise malformed).

An example of a successful response with status code 200 (both methods):

```
{
  "message": "Request received"
}
```

- Finish the deployment”

POST /deployments/{deployment_id}/finish

Possible responses are a deployment description with status code 200 or an error message with code 404 (meaning the deployment was not found).

An example of a successful response with status code 200:

```
{
  "message": "Request received"
}
```

5.5 Licensing information

The PRC is closed-source software, licensed for the PIACERE consortium.

5.6 Download

The code is available for review at Tecnalia’s GitLab, in the private part of the PIACERE project: <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/piacere/private/t23-runtime-controller>

The source code can be provided under request through an email to the address appearing on the website (<https://www.piacere-project.eu/>) in the footer under “Contact Us”. However, no open-source license is granted.

6 Conclusions

This deliverable has described the integration of the PIACERE framework (KR13) v2 and the crucial component of it – the PRC – in detail. The context, architecture, implementation, and usage of PRC were all described.

The current integration involves all tools delivered in year 2 of the PIACERE project, that is the KRs of other technical WPs: WP3-WP6. The tools used in the integration were summarised in this document and important integration points described.

Future versions of this deliverable will adapt the integration to changes in PIACERE tools, continuing to polish the integration details. Some of the plans have been reported in section 4.5.

7 References

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8 APPENDIX: Camunda internals

Since the PRC is largely based on the Camunda Platform, this section is meant to explain some concepts related to Camunda.

Camunda offers full orchestration of BPM from design to execution. This section does not intend to repeat Camunda documentation, but rather to be a PRC-centric guide for a quick start in understanding the PRC internals. Therefore, it starts with a brief description of Camunda Modeler, then it presents the Camunda Platform, focusing on the web interface, while only generically introducing the Process Engine, Process Applications, or Container and Spring Boot integrations.

8.1 Camunda Modeler

Camunda Modeler is a standalone open-source solution for designing automated processes, workflows, and decision requirements diagrams, using Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) and Decision Model and Notation (DMN) standards. Moreover, Camunda Modeler can be used to design Camunda Forms. There is a feature of deploying the model (a new model or a new version of an existing model) directly to a running Camunda Platform instance. The Camunda Modeler interface is presented in Figure 40.

Figure 40 Camunda Modeler

8.2 Camunda Platform

Camunda Platform is a Java-based framework supporting BPMN and DMN. This document focuses on briefly introducing the process and workflow automation with BPMN in order to understand how it is used in PRC.

8.2.1 Camunda Platform web interface applications

Camunda Platform offers a web graphical user interface, consisting of three sections: Admin, Tasklist, and Cockpit. The welcome page is shown in Figure 41.

Figure 41 Camunda web interface: welcome page

Admin is an application dedicated for managing users, groups, and other settings and it will not be discussed in this document.

Tasklist allows working on User Tasks, i.e., tasks that require an interaction with a user, for example by filling some form. Another feature of this one is a possibility to start a new process.

Cockpit is dedicated to monitoring and operations. It contains information about deployed BPMN processes, allows searching through running and ended instances and performing operations on these. User can, for example, find all running instances of a chosen BPMN process and visually track their progress as seen in Figure 42.

The screenshot displays the Camunda Cockpit interface for the 'Piacere Main Process' in its runtime state. The left sidebar provides detailed metadata for the process definition, including its version, key, name, and deployment information. The main area features a BPMN diagram with various tasks and decision points, such as 'Clone repo, prepare and start the project', 'Call external API (GET request) via Camunda http-connector', and 'Perform self-healing'. A table at the bottom lists process instances, with one instance shown in a 'Completed' state.

Figure 42 Camunda web interface: Cockpit

8.2.2 Camunda Platform internals

The core of Camunda Platform is the Process Engine, a component in which modelled and implemented processes are run.

Task implementation approach. Practically, the substantial elements of the BPMN process are events, flow control elements, and tasks. Tasks can be of various types, e.g., user tasks, service tasks, receive tasks, send tasks and others. These types are BPMN definitions and in PRC user and service tasks are mostly applied. Camunda offers several ways of implementing the various types of tasks:

- Expression – evaluates an expression using expression language (precisely, JUEL). Convenient for small pieces of logic directly in BPMN element.
- Script Task – execute a script inside the engine, can be implemented via various scripting languages (e.g. JavaScript, Groovy). Can be embedded in the BPMN or referenced.
- Java Delegate – calls a named bean or Java class implementing *JavaDelegate* interface. It is executed in the same Java Virtual Machine as Camunda Platform. Convenient for more complicated tasks.
- Connector – uses a configurable connector. REST and SOAP connectors are provided. It is configured directly in BPMN. The idea is that the task is performed by some external API.
- External Task – pulls a service task into an external worker threads and informs process engine of completion. Used for heavy and complex tasks, to introduce scalability, hardware implementation, or to avoid timeouts.

All the types external tasks are using push pattern, which means the process engine actively issues a service call (or script). External tasks use a pull pattern, where external worker threads query the engine (via API), do the actual work and notify the engine about completion.

The PRC uses Java Delegates for all its task implementations.

Interacting with the process. One of the essential notions in the BPMN are events. These elements denote some actions that trigger the flow in BPMN diagram. Events can be start elements or inner elements.

- None Event – used only as a start element if no other more specific event is necessary,
- Message Event – used for routing specific incoming message to a specific and unique process instance,
- Timer Event – for making the process wait for or repeat some action,
- Signal Event – for routing a specific signal to all process instances waiting for it,
- Condition Event – the process instance passes this element only when a specific condition is met

It is worth to highlight that messages and signals can be emitted by implementation of tasks, by a BPMN process or externally. The last approach can be used for interacting with Camunda process, for example by executing a REST call to send a message to a specific process instance or a signal to all process instances.

The PRC uses None Events, Message Events, and Timer Events.

Subprocess. There are a few types of subprocesses in Camunda: embedded subprocess (used rather for grouping than introducing additional possibilities), call activities (similar to the embedded subprocess, but invoking a separate BPMN process), and event subprocess. The last type is used in PRC. They can be implemented as interrupting (all active instances of its scope are terminated, and the control is passed to the subprocess) or non-interrupting (can be called multiple times without terminating other instances in the scope). It is run inside the scope, so it has access to all process variables. PRC uses non-interrupting event subprocesses.

Process Instance. When a user starts the process, they create a **process instance**. At the same time, **multiple process instances** can exist. Each process instance is fully independent and exists in its own scope in Camunda Process Engine.